

A STUDY ON PERFORMANCE OF SUBGRADE REINFORCED WITH JUTE FIBERS

Kinga Zangpo¹, Kinley Wangchuk², Nima Dorji³, Pema Wangchuk⁴, Karma Tenzin⁵, Ugyen Dorji⁶, Yeshi Choden⁷,

^{1,2,3,4,5} Undergraduate Students, Department of Civil and Architecture, College of Science and Technology

⁶ Lecturer, Department of Civil and Architecture, College of Science and Technology

⁷ Assistant lecturer, Department of Civil and Architecture, College of Science and Technology

*Email: 02012013094.cst@rub.edu.bt¹, 02012013030.cst@rub.edu.bt², 02012013043.cst@rub.edu.bt³, 02012013050.cst@rub.edu.bt⁴, 02012013023.cst@rub.edu.bt⁵, ugyendorji.cst@rub.edu.bt⁶ & yeshichoden.cst@rub.edu.bt⁷

Abstract: *The performance of pavement depends on the strength of subgrade. The weak subgrade results into greater thickness of pavement. This research aims to improve of subgrade strength by reinforcing soil with jute fibers. The percentages of jute fibers taken are 0.25%, 0.50%, 0.75% and 1% with aspect ratios 8.33 and 16.67. Soaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR) was performed to obtain values for different percentages of jute fibers. The CBR value of natural soil increases, when it was reinforced with jute fibers. This increase is substantial at fiber content 0.50% and 0.75% of aspect ratio 8.33 and 16.67 respectively. The thickness of various layer of pavement was carried out as per IRC:37-2001 and the pavement thickness chart provided by the Department of Road (DoR). Cost analysis was done only for the pavement thickness determined as per the thickness chart provided by DoR. There was maximum reduction in cost at fiber content 0.50% and 0.75% for aspect ratio 8.33 and 16.67 respectively. Reinforcement of soil with jute fibers is economically advantages and is observed to be a viable solution for the construction of roads with weak subgrade.*

Keywords: California Bearing ratio, Aspect Ratio, Jute Fibers, Subgrade.

1. INTRODUCTION

The socio-economic growth and progress depends upon the development of adequate transportation system in the country (Hossain *et al* 2015). Good transportation system provides safe, economical, efficient transportation facility for the travel of passengers and transportation of goods. These transportation is achieved through economical pavement design. The subgrade, which is the lower most layer plays a vital role in the strength of the flexible pavement. Weak subgrade results in greater thickness of the pavement layer which results in increase in the cost of construction. The properties of the soil differ throughout the length of the road. Poor natural soils are unsuitable for the construction of road pavements. In order to resolve these issues,

new techniques of construction and soil stabilization are explored.

The natural materials such as jute, coir, sisal and bamboo are used to improve the performance of subgrade (Singh & Bagra, 2015). This study incorporates jute fibers as the reinforcing material to improve the subgrade strength as jutes are available in the market and biodegradable. Different percentages of jute fibers were reinforced with the natural soil and their corresponding CBR values were found out. Depending upon the fiber content that gives maximum CBR values, flexible pavement was designed and the cost effectiveness was then analyzed in comparison to the conventional flexible pavement.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study are:

- i. To compare the performance of subgrade with and without inclusion of jute fibers based on the CBR value.
- ii. To estimate and analyze the cost effectiveness of flexible pavement with and without inclusion of jute fiber.
- iii. To check the applications of jute fibers in flexible pavement design.

3. METHODOLOGY

A span of 0.50 km length of road between Rinchening check post and Reldri Higher Secondary School junction was considered in this study. The road falls under Primary National Highway (PNH) according to the Road Pavement Standards set by the Department of Roads (DoR). The road connects from Phuentsholing to Pasakha, where most of the industries in Bhutan are located.

Figure-1 Study area for the project

3.1 Materials

3.1.1 Soil

Five soil samples were collected at a frequency of 100 m from the study area as shown in **Figure-1**. The soil samples were dug and collected, at a depth of 500mm from the top portion of the highway as per IRC:37-2001.

3.1.2 Reinforcement

The jute fibers were collected from the local market. Two different aspect ratios of jute fibers 8.33 (length=25 mm, diameter=3 mm) and 16.67 (L=50 mm, D=3 mm) were used for the study.

Figure-2 Collection of soil

Figure-3 Jute fibers used for reinforcement

4. TESTING OF SPECIMEN

The compaction tests were performed for the collected five soil samples to obtain the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and Maximum Dry Density (MDD) as per Indian Standard (IS 2720: Part-VIII). Soaked CBR tests were performed for five samples and the sample, which gave minimum CBR value, was considered for this study and its physical properties are given in **Table-1**. The selected soil sample was then reinforced with different percentages of 0.25%, 0.50%, 0.75% & 1% of jute fibers. The OMC for each fiber contents were obtained and the corresponding CBR values were determined after soaking the sample for four days.

Table-1 Physical properties of selected sample

Property	Result
Specific gravity	2.55
Liquid Limit	31.13%
Plastic Limit	21.15%
Plasticity Index	9.98%
OMC	7.73
MDD	20.24
CBR	6.79

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Compaction test

With the addition of 0.25% jute fiber of 8.33 and 16.67 aspect ratio, MDD reduces from 20.70kN/m³ to 20.66kN/m³ and 20.62kN/m³ respectively and correspondingly OMC increases from 6.9% to 7.10% and 7.20%. MDD decreases until 19.72kN/m³ with increase in OMC to 8.15% and until 19.64kN/m³ with increase in OMC to 8.30% at 1.0% fiber content for 8.33 and 16.67 aspect ratio respectively as shown in **Figure-4**. The inclusion of the jute fibers replaces certain portion of soil which has the higher density and hence tends to reduce MDD with increase in fiber content.

Figure-4 Effect of fiber content on MDD

5.2 California Bearing Ratio

Maximum CBR value observed is 21.98% at 0.5% fiber content and 13.77% at 0.75% fiber content of aspect ratio 8.33 and 16.67 respectively as shown in **Figure-5**. The CBR value of soil increases with the addition of jute fiber and further addition of fiber decreases the CBR value, showing parabolic relationship. This is due to the fact that the effect of fiber gets exhausted after reaching the maximum value and results in increase of void ratio, which then decreases the CBR value. Thus, further addition of jute fiber becomes counterproductive after the maximum value.

Figure-5 Effect of fiber on CBR value

5.3 Pavement design

In the present study, pavement was designed as per IRC:37-2001 and the pavement thickness chart provided by the Department of Roads (DoR), Ministry of Work and Human Settlement (MoWHS). The thickness for various layers of pavement are determined based on the CBR value obtained for the selected sample reinforced with different percentages of jute fibers. The section of different layers of pavement are shown excluding the subgrade thickness of 500 mm.

5.3.1 Design based on IRC:37-2001

For the pavement design based on IRC:37-2001, the design data assumed are given below:

- i. Initial traffic in the year of completion of construction = 300CV/day
- ii. Traffic growth rate = 7.5 percent
- iii. Design life = 15 years
- iv. Vehicle Damage Factor (VDF) = 1.5

The design traffic is computed using the following equation:

$$N = \frac{365 \times [(1+r)^n - 1]}{r} \times A \times D \times F$$

Where,

- N = Cumulative number of standard axles to be catered for in the design in terms of msa.
- A = Initial traffic in the year of completion of construction in terms of the number of CVPD

- D = Lane distribution factor
- F = Vehicle damage factor
- n = Design life in years
- r = Annual growth rate of CV

The pavement section for natural soil with CBR value 6.79% is as shown in **Figure-6**. Similarly, the pavement section for the soil sample reinforced with 0.50% fiber content of 8.33 aspect ratio which gives the maximum CBR value of 21.98% is shown in **Figure-7**.

5.3.2 Design based on DoR

The pavement section for the plain soil with CBR value 6.79% is shown in **Figure-8**. Similarly, the pavement section for the soil sample reinforced with 0.50% of fiber content of 8.33 aspect ratio which gives the maximum CBR value of 21.98% as shown in **Figure-9**.

Figure-6 Pavement section of natural soil (IRC:37-2001)

Figure-7 Pavement section of soil reinforced with 0.5% jute fiber of 8.33 aspect ratio (IRC:37-2001)

Figure-8 Pavement section of natural soil (DoR)

Figure-9 Pavement section of soil reinforced with 0.5% jute fiber of 8.33 aspect ratio (DoR)

From the above results, it is observed that the pavement thickness determined as per IRC:37-2001 differs from the thickness determined based on pavement thickness chart provided by the Department of Roads. Pavement thickness chart provided by the Department of Roads has groups of CBR values such as 5 to 7%, for which the thickness of the pavement layers remains same i.e., CBR value 5%, 6% and 7% will have same thickness of pavement layers. The maximum CBR value extends to 30% and for greater than 30%, the thickness remains same as 30%. Whereas in IRC:37-2001, there is different ranges of CBR values from 2% to 10%. The maximum CBR range is 10% and CBR greater than it remains as 10% only.

5.4 Cost Analysis

The cost is done for the pavement thickness determined as per the thickness chart provided by the Department of Roads only. The estimated cost of the pavement is the total cost for 0.50 km length of road considered for the project.

The cost estimation for the conventional method of construction, without jute reinforcement, is shown in **Table-2**. The estimation was done based on Bhutan Schedules of Rates (BSR 2015). **Table-3** shows the estimation for the pavement when the subgrade is reinforced with 0.50% jute fiber of 8.33 aspect ratio.

Table-2 Cost Estimation for the conventional method of construction

SI No.	Pavement Composition	Length (m)	width (m)	Height (m)	Quantity	Unit	Rate (Nu.)	Cost (Nu.)	Total cost (Nu.)
1	AC Course	500	7.5		3750	m ²	504.05	1890187.5	6943297.5
2	DBM Course	500	7.5		3750	m ²	671.96	2519850	
3	WMM Course	500	7.5	200	750	m ³	1759.65	1319737.5	
4	GSB Course	500	7.5	225	843.75	m ³	1367.76	1154047.5	
5	Subgrade	500	7.5	500	1875	m ³	31.72	59475	

Table-3 Cost Estimation for jute reinforcement of 0.50% fiber of 8.33 aspect ratio

S.N	Pavement Composition	Length (m)	Width (m)	Height (m)	Quantity	Unit	Rate (Nu.)	Cost (Nu.)	Total cost (Nu.)	Saving in cost (%)
1	AC Course	500	7.5		3750	m ²	504.05	1890187.5	6302628	9.23
2	DBM Course	500	7.5		3750	m ²	671.96	2519850		
3	WMM Course	500	7.5	200	750	m ³	1759.65	1319737.5		
4	GSB Course	500	7.5	100	375	m ³	1367.76	512910		
5	Subgrade	500	7.5	500	1875	m ³	31.72	59475		
6	0.5% Jute Fiber of Soil	(0.5/100) x 1875 = 9.375				kg	50	468.75		

*The rate of jute fiber was taken from the market per kg

The sample without jute fiber has the highest cost of construction of Nu. 6,943,297.5/- due to its higher thickness of pavement composition. However, the cost of construction drops to Nu. 6,302,628.75/- with the inclusion of 0.50% jute fiber of aspect ratio 8.33 with the subgrade. This is due to the reduction of pavement thickness from 525mm to 400mm excluding the subgrade thickness of 500mm.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the present study, the CBR value of soil increases with the inclusion of jute fiber and the increase is maximum (more than 200% over natural soil) at fiber content 0.50% for aspect ratio 8.33. The aspect ratio of 8.33 is found to give higher CBR value than the aspect ratio 16.67, which indicates the effect of the length of the jute fiber of same diameter.

Reinforcement of soil by jute fibers is economically advantageous as it is cheap, available in the market and reduce the cost of construction of flexible pavement by 9.23% of its cost by conventional method. Therefore, jute fiber is found to be an effective solution for the construction of roads with weak subgrades.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Different percentages of jute fiber and aspect ratios could be used to see the effect besides the mentioned percentages and aspect ratios. Further more research is required for the test on jute fibers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express their gratitude to Royal University of Bhutan and College of Science and Technology in particular, for providing invaluable opportunity and continued support in the course of the research.

The authors also express their gratitude to Mr. Ugyen Dorji, Guide, for his guidance and Ms. Yeshe Choden, Co-Guide, for her support in the times of the study. The authors are also indebted to Dr. Raju Sarkar, Faculty of Civil Engineering

and Architecture Department (CEAD), for his constructive feedbacks. Thanks are also to Mr. Khampa, Technician, CEAD, for his support in laboratory experiments.

REFERENCES

Aggarwal, P. & Sharma, B. (2011). *Application of Jute Fiber in the Improvement of Subgrade Characteristics*. International Journal on Transportation and Urban Development.

Ghosh, B., Ramesh, V. & Vibhuti, R.B. (2014). *Improvement of Soil Characteristics Using Jute Geo-Textile*. International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research (IJSETR), Volume 3, Issue 7.

Hossain, A., Hossain, S. & Hasan, K. (2015). *Application of Jute Fiber for the Improvement of Subgrade Characteristics*. American Journal of Civil Engineering ISSN: 2330- 8737, Volume 3.

Hossain, A., Hossain, S. & Hasan, K. (2015). *Application of Jute Fiber for the Improvement of Subgrade Characteristics*. American Journal of Civil Engineering ISSN:2330- 8737, Volume 3.

IRC 37, "Guidelines for the design of flexible pavements (Second Revision)", Indian Road Congress, New Delhi, 2001.

Kumar, D., Nigam, S., Nangia, A. & Tiwari, S. (2015). *Improvement in CBR Values of Soil Reinforced with Jute layer*. International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research (IJETR) ISSN: 2321-0869, Volume-3, Issue-5.

Sarkar, R., Daalia, A., Narang, K., Garg, S., Agarwal, P. & Mudgal, A (2016). *Cost Effectiveness of Flexible Pavement on Stabilized Expansive Soils*. International Journal of GEOMATE. Vol.10, No.1 (Sl. No. 19).

Singh, H. P. & Bagra, M. (2013). *Improvement in CBR Value of Soil Reinforced with Jute Fiber*. International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol.2, Issue 8.